

NEW CONCEPTS TO REDUCE THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF FLOOR PANELS IN CIVIL AIRCRAFTS

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SUSTAINABILITY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY AS MAIN STAKEHOLDER

- Rising interest to implement sustainable concepts within the aeronautic sector caused by different drivers:

Legislation Manufacturers are forced to demonstrate recycling options for their parts

Social Increasing social awareness for sustainability

Market Competitiveness combined with sustainability

Three action areas to increase sustainability within the aeronautic sector

- **Planification:** Weight, Choice of Materials
- **Production:** Production process efficiency
- **Use:** Route planning, weight restrictions, Fuel

Choice of the part within the aircraft and action area

DEMONSTRATION PART:

Floor panels of civil aircrafts

LOAD CASE:

Semi-Structural part

CRITICALNESS:

Classification as an B-part regarding the criticalness

Assumptions:

- Optimised production concepts as the smallest part of the emission along the life cycle
- Use phase is considered as optimised under the given use case of an highly used aircraft

Figure 1: The area of the floor panels is marked in blue [1]

The development of Floor Panels over the years

A Timeline of used Materials within Floor Panels

Past

Present

Future

Different Challenges are addressed by the Concept

Approach and preliminary Tests

DAMAGE INVESTIGATION OF CORK REINFORCED SANDWICH PARTS

Casual sandwich panel

Cork reinforced sandwich panel

© FIBRE

The damage behaviour and the fracture strain were largely improved under 3 points bending loads, but the bending stiffness and strength were reduced.

Panel	Bending strength [MPa]	Failure strain [%]
3D_10	47.9 ± 7	26.3 ± 4
cork	36.8 ± 1.6	62.9 ± 11

Different semi-finished Parts as Textiles for the Face Sheets

RCF-YARN PRODUCTION AND RCF- NON-CRIMP FABRICS

Opening of rCF
optional: mixing with
thermoplastic fibres
Mixing ratio rCF/CoPA:
90/10 %

Increasing the
fibre
orientation

Sliver formation

Solidification

Suitable for further
processing into components
using standard composite
production processes © CarboYarn

Yarn and fabric production is **feasible**, but the **quality** of the produced yarns is crucial for good results.

Non-Crimp Fabric Production

Non-Crimp Fabric production from rCF-Slivers

Post-Processing

Sliver opening

Machine preparation

Sliver placement

NCF production

Winding

Assembling and Infusion

Opened slivers on a card board

Prepared Machine with first placed slivers

Positioned slivers on Non-Crimp Fabric machine

Warp-knitted semi-finished part

Evenness of produced Slivers after Drawfting

Results:

- Measurement of sliver pieces after processing
- Continuous process of sliver production vs. discontinuous testing method
- Between 7 and 18 % standard deviation
- The higher the set areal weight the more stable gets the process between the beginning and the end phase

First good results, but:

Sliver evenness and **fibre alignment** have to be improved

15 gsm slivers on a light table

30 gsm slivers on a light table

Manufacturing and Testing of the developed Concept

Validation of the Concept following an ascending testing Pyramid

VALIDATION APPROACH

- I. Characterisation of slivers or yarns
- II. Characterisation of semi-finished parts
- III. Testing of flat composite structures
- IV. Testing of sandwich plates

TESTED PROPERTIES

- Evenness
- Tensile Properties
- Impact Properties
- Acoustic Properties
- Insert Properties
- Peeling Test
- 4-Point Bending Properties
- Further

ADVANTAGES OF THE CONCEPT USING VACUUM INFUSION

- No need to adapt the layup due to the porosity of the cork layer
- Insert potting not necessary due to the foam core

Conclusion

NOVELTY OF THE FLOOR PANEL CONCEPT

Material:

- ✓ Using rCF-Facesheets and cork as an interlayer
- ✓ Bio-based resin-systems

Lightweight:

- ✓ Cork interlayer improves the impact properties
- ✓ Foam core erases the need for potting of inserts

Sustainability:

- ✓ Bio-based and recycled materials

Open points:

- Reproducibility depending on the input material flows
- Evenness of the input material
- Mechanical properties

Supported by:

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